

Design and In Vitro Evaluation of Benzydamine Hydrochloride Effervescent Tablets for Vaginal Delivery

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ABSTRACT

Benzydamine hydrochloride (BEN) has immediate action on vaginal inflammation, also has an activity against *Trichomonas vaginalis* and *Gardnerella vaginalis*. Of vaginal dosage forms, patients are known to better tolerate gels. However, the direct application of gels onto the infected sites of the vagina might be difficult, inconvenient as well as need frequent dosing. Effervescent vaginal tablets offer convenience of dosing methods of tablet and disintegrate rapidly to prevent vaginal clearance due to gravity. Sodium bicarbonate and citric acid were added as effervescent mixture, to increase disintegration time of the tablet; Lactose as diluents; sodium lauryl sulphate as foaming agent and starch as disintegrant. Three formulations (F1, F2, and F3) were prepared by varying concentration of starch. Tablets were evaluated for hardness, disintegration time, friability, dissolution profile and effect on pH value of medium. F1 shows maximum disintegration time approximately 20 minutes, F2 and F3 shows 15 minutes and 11 minutes respectively. Dissolution profile of F1 shows 74.48% release, F2 and F3 shows 78.89% and 99.94% release within 8 minutes respectively, thus F3 formulation shows nearly complete release within 8 minutes and lower disintegration time. Formulations showed pH change of the medium within normal range of vaginal fluid (pH 3.2-4.8). Effervescent vaginal tablet will surely enhance patient compliance.

Keywords: Benzydamine, effervescent vaginal tablet, vaginitis.

INTRODUCTION

Vaginal route of drug administration is commonly used for the local therapy of specific gynaecological diseases. Delivery via the vagina has some additional advantages over oral delivery: the avoidance of hepatic first-pass metabolism, a reduction in the incidence and severity of gastrointestinal and/or hepatic side effects [1,2]. Considerable progress has been made over the last ten years in investigating and developing novel vaginal drug delivery systems with desirable distribution, bioadhesion, retention and release characteristics. Attempts are being made to develop novel vaginal drug delivery systems that can meet the clinical as well as the patient's requirements [3-6].

Vaginitis is one of the most frequent gynaecological diseases. Vaginitis is an inflammation of the vagina. It can result in discharge, itching and pain, and is often associated with an irritation or infection of the vulva. Common infectious forms of vaginitis include bacterial vaginosis, vulvovaginal candidiasis, and trichomoniasis[7]. Vaginitis by *Trichomonas vaginalis* is the most common sexually transmitted infection, but vaginitis can be also the result of candidiasis and infection by mixed bacterial flora [8].

Benzydamine hydrochloride is a nonsteroid anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), has immediate action on

vaginal inflammation [9, 10]. Benzydamine also found display an activity against *Trichomonas vaginalis* and *Gardnerella vaginalis* at concentrations in the region of 10-20 µg/ml, while its activity against fungi and the other bacteria manifests itself only at concentrations that are 10-20 times as great [11, 12].

Marketed vaginal preparations of benzydamine hydrochloride are vaginal douche (0.1% w/v aqueous solution) and vaginal cream (0.5% w/w). These dosage forms suffer from disadvantages like these vaginal preparations are messy to apply, can leak in the undergarments and give an uncomfortable feeling to the user. Moreover, semi-solid formulations may not allow accurate drug dosing due to non-uniform distribution in and leakage from the vaginal cavity [13, 14].

Vaginal tablets are easy to apply by the user and provide accurate drug dosing, but vaginal disintegration of conventional tablets can be slow and due to gravity the tablets are rapidly cleared from the vagina [15]. So there is need to increase disintegration time of tablet. In this study Effervescent vaginal tablets were formulated. Effervescent mixture was added to increase disintegration time of tablet.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Benzylamine hydrochloride was gifted by Elder pharmaceuticals Ltd., Navi Mumbai, India. All other chemicals were of pharmacopoeial grade. Double distilled water was used whenever required.

Preparation of EVTs

Granules containing the active principle were prepared by mixing benzylamine hydrochloride and maize starch (half quantity) together with an aqueous solution of starch paste (10%). The wet mass was forced through a screen (710 μ). The granules were then dried to constant weight and sieved again. Colloidal silica was added thereto and the mixture was mixed. Separately, granules containing citric acid were prepared from lactose and maize starch (half quantity) together with an aqueous solution of starch paste (10%). The dry Sodium bicarbonate moistened with 16% dispersion of egg albumin and mixed. The wet mass was forced through a screen (710 μ). These three granules were dried to constant weight and sieved again. They were protected from moisture. Before making the tablets, all the ingredient, with the exception of the granulated sodium bicarbonate, were thoroughly dried by heating in an oven for 2 hours at about 540C to 600C. Previously dried above three granules and other ingredients were mixed thoroughly[16, 17].

Table 1: Compositions of EVT formulations (data in % w/w)

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3
Benzylamine hydrochloride	10	10	10
Lactose	30	30	30
Maize starch	5	12.5	20
Sodium bicarbonate	30	30	30
Citric acid anhydrous	26	26	26
Sodium lauryl sulphate	1	1	1
Magnesium stearate	0.6	0.6	0.6
Colloidal silica	0.4	0.4	0.4

Granules compressed with punch having punch size 12.5 mm and hardness adjusted to 8-9 kg/cm². Each tablet contains 10 mg benzylamine hydrochloride.

Evaluation of formulated tablets

EVTS were evaluated for Thickness, Weight variation, Hardness, Drug content, Disintegration time and Friability. Tablets further evaluated for following parameters.

In-vitro benzylamine hydrochloride release study

Release studies were carried out using the USP 29 dissolution apparatus II paddle type (LABINDIA DISSO, Digital tablet dissolution test apparatus), in 900 ml phosphate buffer solution (PBS, pH 4.0) as the dissolution medium. The rate of stirring was 50 rpm. And the medium temperature was maintained at 37 \pm 0.50C. At each sampling interval, 5 ml of the dissolution medium was withdrawn and replaced by an equal volume of fresh

PBS. Benzylamine hydrochloride was determined at 304 nm by using a UV-2450 spectrophotometer (SHIMADZU) 18.

Effect on pH value of medium

The effect of EVTs on pH value of phosphate buffer (pH 4.0) was investigated. The tablet was placed within 40 ml of medium, and the pH value of medium was measured and recorded till complete tablet get disintegrated [18].

Foam formation

In this test 2 ml of distilled water was put into cylindrical glass tube. This water was kept at normal body temperature. Dry tablet was put in to water without stirring. Foam formation was visually observed [17].

Physicochemical interaction studies

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

DSC analysis was performed using Thermal Analyzer DSC60 (SHIMADZU) by taking 2 to 5 mg samples. Sample were hermetically sealed aluminium pan and heated at a rate of 10°C/min conducted over a temperature range of 30°C to 300°C under nitrogen with flow rate of 10°C/min. Before the analysis all samples were vacuum dried for 24 hours.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) Interpretation

The infrared spectra sample was recorded by FTIR spectrometer 84005 (SHIMADZU), equipped with Interferometer detector. Samples were prepared by KBr disc method (2 mg sample in 100 mg KBr) and examined in the transmission mode. Each spectrum was measured over a frequency range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹. The software used for the data analysis was Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 3.02. The peaks obtained in the spectra were then compared with corresponding functional groups in the structures of benzylamine hydrochloride.

Stability Study

Each batch of 5 tablets were wrapped in aluminium foil and stored at 40 \square 20C temperature with relative humidity of 75 \square 5%. The sampling was done after three month and evaluation was done for appearance, thickness, hardness and drug content.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the physical parameters of the tablets were found practically within control.

Disintegration time for F1 was found to be approximately 20 minutes, for F2 15 minutes and for F3 11 minutes. This tablet is substantially wholly dissolved or disintegrated in about twice its weight of water. The tablet is provided with sodium bicarbonate and citric acid anhydrous which form a harmless gas when tablet is contacted with water

The effect of tablet on pH of vaginal tract was determined in vitro using phosphate buffer pH 4. All three formulations showed pH change within normal pH range of vaginal fluid (pH 3.2- pH 4.8).

Fatty alcohol sulphate is used as a wetting and dispersing agent to reduce surface tension. Sodium lauryl sulphate along with effervescent mixture forms dense viscous and stable foam when tablet get disintegrated. After complete disintegration of tablet solution become viscous due to presence of starch. Formed foam assists in retention of drug by entrapping drug into foam.

Lactose as diluent, act as substrate for lactobacilli to produce lactic acid which increases vaginal pH. Starch is acting as disintegration agent (5%-20%).

Dissolution profile of EVTs is shown in Fig. 1. From release profile it can be seen that the Formulation F1 shows 66.25%

release, F2 shows 78.89% and F3 shows 99.94% release within 8 minutes, thus F3 formulation shows nearly complete release within 8 minutes.

The parameters studied for evaluation of EVT's were given in Table 2.

Formulation code	F1	F2	F3
Thickness (mm)	3.625±0.1320	3.695±0.1515	3.605±0.2523
Average weight (mg)	839.34 ± 0.4923	911.98 ± 0.3987	978.67 ± 0.4323
Hardness (kg/cm ²)	7.76±0.1673	7.8±0.1414	7.76±0.2608
% Drug Content	98.555 ± 0.6969	98.84 ± 1.236	97.93 ± 0.6781
Disintegration Time (min)	20.44 ± 0.9945	15.69 ± 0.8967	10.93 ± 1.073
% Friability	0.256	0.276	0.321
Effect on pH of medium	4.48	4.61	4.57

Fig. 1: In vitro release profile of EVT's

Fig. 2: Overlay spectra of benzydamine hydrochloride and EVT (F3)

Physicochemical interaction studies

These studies were carried out on formulation F3.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC thermogram overlay of benzydamine hydrochloride and EVT (F3) is shown in Fig. 2. The DSC curve of benzydamine hydrochloride shows a sharp endothermic peak at 162.250C. Whereas EVT-F3 given short endothermic peak at 147.920C and deep endothermic peak at 191.290C which clearly indicates the peak of HPMC. DSC thermogram showed shifting of drug peak from 162.260C to 147.920C, the reason behind that the drug may be dissolved in the polymer matrix before reaching its fusion temperature, the drug may affect the lattice energy of the polymer, the drug may be present in crystalline or amorphous or in both form whereas polymers may be present in eutectic form, this

happens due to the compression force. This indicates that there may be physical interaction, but no any chemical reaction.

FTIR spectrum of EVT (F3)

The interaction between the drug and the excipient often leads to identifiable changes in the FTIR profile of formulation. To check for any interactions occurring in optimized formulation, their FTIR spectra were recorded (Fig.3). Slight difference was seen in the position of the absorption bands of benzydamine hydrochloride occurred in spectra of EVT (F3). However, the major characteristic peaks for benzydamine hydrochloride (Fig. 4) were still present indicating that there was no any chemical interaction between drug and excipients. Important vibrations detected in the spectrum of EVT (F3) are shown in Table 3.

Fig. 3: FTIR spectrum of EVT (F3)

Fig. 4: Structure of benzydamine hydrochloride

Table 3: Identified functional groups present in EVT (F3).

Principle observed values (cm ⁻¹)	peak of Spectrum of Benzydamine hydrochloride (group)
1028.02	C-N bending
1166.97	C-O stretching in ether
1437.02	C-H deformation
1558.54	-NH bending in amines
2359.02	C-N stretching

Stability Study

The short term stability study of selected formulation EVT (F3) was performed as per ICH (International conference on harmonisation) guidelines at temperature 40° C and 75% RH for three month. The results of stability study (Table 4) revealed that drug content and all other parameters were within the acceptable limit.

Table 4: Evaluation of formulation EVT (F3) kept for stability at 40°C /75%RH.

Parameter	After 3 months
Appearance	White colour
Thickness (mm)	3.60
Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	7.8
Drug content (%)	99.56

CONCLUSION

In present study effervescent vaginal tablets were successfully prepared. Sodium bicarbonate and citric acid anhydrous decreases disintegration time, decrease chances of getting cleared from vagina due to gravity. Sodium lauryl sulphate forms dense and stable foam when tablet get disintegrated. Formulation F3 shows complete release within 8 minutes. Effervescent vaginal tablet will deliver accurate dosing to vaginal tract, with uniform distribution, with ease of administration and increased contact time of drug as compared to vaginal douche.

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